

Synthesis and Reactions of Some α -Cyano Aroyl Anils

D. R. GUPTA & A. C. OJHA

Department of Chemistry, U. P. Agricultural University, Pantnagar, Nainital
and

Sahu-Jain College, Najibabad. (U.P.)

Received 24 November 1970

A number of new α -cyano aroyl anils (III) have been synthesised by condensing pyridinium iodides (I) of substituted acetophenones with *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline (II) and subsequent treatment with sodium cyanide through the following reactions :

In an earlier communication, a number of pyridinium iodides of substituted acetophenones were reported^{1,2}.

where $x, x_1, x_2, x_3 = \text{H}, \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{OH}, \text{CH}_3$ or NO_2 .

The present communication concerns with the synthesis and characterisation of α -cyano aroyl anils obtained from pyridinium iodides of 2 : 4-dihydroxy-, 2 : 5-dihydroxy-, 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-, 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro-, 2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo-, 2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo-, 2-bromo-4-nitro-, *p*-nitro acetophenones and naphthyl methyl ketones.

TABLE 1
Cyano aroylanils derived from substituted acetophenones and p-nitroso dimethylaniline

Sl. No.	Name of the α -Cyano compounds	Colour	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	% Nitrogen		% Halogens	
						Required	Found	Required	Found
1	α -Cyano 2 : 4-dihydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_3$	190	65	13.59	13.23	—	—
2	α -Cyano 2 : 5-dihydroxy Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Dark Brown	$C_{17}H_{15}N_3O_3$	178	66	13.59	13.12	—	—
3	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-5-methyl Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{18}H_{17}N_3O_2$	148	40.25	13.68	13.42	—	—
4	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-5-chloro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{14}N_3O_2Cl$	152	50	—	—	10.87	10.42
5	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-5-bromo Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{14}N_3O_2Br$	159	45	—	—	21.50	21.18
6	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Reddish Green	$C_{18}H_{16}N_3O_2Cl$	192	35.5	—	—	10.36	10.12
7	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-3-bromo-5-chloro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{13}N_3O_2ClBr$	186	35	—	—	28.41	28.03
8	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-bromo Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{18}H_{16}N_3O_2Br$	164	36	—	—	20.72	20.41
9	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo-Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{13}N_3O_2Br_2$	163	30	—	—	35.47	35.09
10	α -Cyano-2-hydroxy-3-chloro-5-bromo Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{13}N_3O_2ClBr$	180	37	—	—	28.41	28.15
11	α -Cyano-2-bromo-4-nitro Phenacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_4H_7N_4O_3$	166	56	—	—	19.95	19.72
12	α -Cyano- <i>p</i> -nitro Phenacylidene amino anil	Red	$C_{17}H_{14}N_4O_3$	180	70	17.72	17.42	—	—
13	α -Cyano Naphthacylidene <i>p</i> -dimethyl amino anil	Red	$C_{21}H_{17}N_3O$	146	65	12.10	11.82	—	—

TABLE 2
Derivatives of α -cyano substituted phenacylidene p-dimethyl amino anils
 OXIMES SEMI-CARBAZONES

Sl.* No.	Colour	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		% Halogens		Colour	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		% Halogens	
			Required	Found	Required	Found			Required	Found	Required	Found
1	Brown	170	17.28	17.01	—	—	Orange	146	18.02	17.81	—	—
2	Brown	174	17.28	16.85	—	—	Orange	141	18.02	17.65	—	—
3	Reddish	153	17.39	17.11	—	—	Orange	135	23.07	22.37	—	—
4	Dark Brown	162	—	—	10.10	9.80	Red	158	—	—	9.23	9.25
5	Brown	155	—	—	20.87	20.53	Red	162	—	—	18.64	18.28
6	Red	198	—	—	10.42	10.12	Orange	168	—	—	7.52	7.18
7	Red	178	—	—	27.40	27.03	Red	156	—	—	24.91	24.73
8	Orange	159	—	—	19.95	19.68	Orange	165	—	—	18.05	17.77
9	Red	168	—	—	36.48	36.02	Red	158	—	—	31.49	31.02
10	Orange	186	—	—	27.40	27.01	Orange	162	—	—	24.91	24.68
11	Red	172	—	—	19.42	19.16	Red	164	—	—	17.46	17.12
12	Red	205	23.47	23.12	—	—	Orange	198	25.85	25.13	—	—
13	Red	174	16.38	16.13	—	—	Red	148	21.87	21.23	—	—

* Sl. No. indicate anils given in Table No. 1.

TABLE 3

Sl.* No.	Colour	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		% Halogens		Colour	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		% Halogens	
			Required	Found	Required	Found			Required	Found	Required	Found
1	Red	156	17.54	16.06	—	—	Red	190	20.04	19.18	—	—
2	Red	148	17.54	16.10	—	—	Red	182	20.04	19.63	—	—
3	Brown	140	17.63	17.18	—	—	Red	150	20.08	19.64	—	—
4	Red	157	—	—	8.53	8.16	Red	188	—	—	6.98	6.61
5	Brown	165	—	—	17.49	17.18	Orange	160	—	—	14.64	14.23
6	Brown	188	—	—	8.24	8.01	Red	176	—	—	6.87	6.38
7	Brown	176	—	—	23.26	23.01	Red	168	—	—	19.71	19.24
8	Red	159	—	—	16.61	16.25	Yellow	193	—	—	14.13	13.82
9	Red	178	—	—	29.57	29.30	Orange	175	—	—	30.50	30.09
10	Orange	168	—	—	23.26	23.19	Orange	172	—	—	19.71	19.28
11	Red	182	—	—	16.46	16.18	Orange	182	—	—	13.74	13.25
12	Brown	155	20.38	20.04	—	—	Red	140	23.30	23.02	—	—
13	Brown	168	16.78	16.16	—	—	Dark-red	188	19.32	19.02	—	—

* Sl. No. indicate anils given in Table No. 1.

Synthesis of α -cyano substituted aroyl anils : Pyridinium iodides of ketones (0.05 mol) were dissolved in 50% alcohol (20 ml) at 30° and treated with *p*-nitrosodimethyl aniline (0.04 mol) in absolute alcohol (20 ml). To the reaction mixture was added a 10% sodium cyanide solution (10 ml) and the products were kept in a freezing mixture. The solids thus obtained were filtered and crystallised from ethanol. These α -cyano phenacylidene *p*-dimethyl amino-anils are soluble in 50% ethanol, acetonitrile, chloroform and acetone but practically insoluble in ether and water. The characteristics of α -cyano aroyl anils are recorded in Table 1.

*Characterisation of α -cyano phenacylidene *p*-dimethyl amino anils* : Oximes, semi-carbazones, phenylhydrazones and 2 : 4-dinitro phenyl hydrazones were prepared by the usual methods. Oximes and semi-carbazones were crystallised from ethanol while hydrazones from benzene and toluene. The characteristics of the derivatives are listed in Tables 2 and 3.

These cyano phenacylidene *p*-dimethyl amino-anils cause a sharp colour change on reacting with Lewis acids and exhibit bathochromism in the molecule, thus offering a possibility for chelate formation. The probable mechanism for the chelation has been suggested as follows :

The oximes of some of these α -cyano anils produce colour changes with several metal ions and could, therefore, offer a possibility of being employed as analytical reagents.

The authors are thankful to Sri M. K. Jain, Principal, Sahu Jain College, Najibabad for encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. D. R. Gupta, Y. Singh and H. D. Tayal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **45**, 164.
2. D. R. Gupta and A. C. Ojha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, **48**, 811.